

The polarographic technique can be successfully employed for the identification of *cis-trans* isomers of metal complexes. Crow and Westwood^{1,2} have prepared the *cis-trans* isomers of Rhodium (III) and Cobaltic ions separately and got two distinct waves for the two forms of the complex.

The author has prepared the *cis-trans* isomers of Platinum (II) complex of the type $[\text{Pt}(\text{NH}_3)(\text{NO}_2)\text{Cl}_2]^-$ and examined them polarographically. The results of his observation are given in this paper.

Experimental

All the reagents used were of AnalaR/BDH grade. The solutions were prepared in conductivity water. An automatic pen recording C.I.C. (India) polarograph was used to record the polarograms. The pH of the solutions was measured using a Phillips pH-meter.

All the observations were made at room temperature, 27°.

The *cis* and *Trans* isomers of Platinum(II) complex of the type $[\text{Pt}(\text{NH}_3)(\text{NO}_2)\text{Cl}_2]^-$ were prepared³ and their polarograms were recorded⁴. The ionic strength and the pH of the solutions was kept constant; using KCl solution and a buffer solution for their respective adjustments.

Results and Discussion

It is observed that each of the *cis* and *trans* isomers of $[\text{Pt}(\text{NH}_3)(\text{NO}_2)\text{Cl}_2]^-$ gives a separate reversible cathodic polarographic wave. The details of the polarographic study are given below:

Supporting-Electrolyte	— 1M KCl
Maximum suppressor	— 0.001% gelatin
Platinum (II)	— $5 \times 10^{-4} M$
Ammonia	— $5 \times 10^{-4} M$
NO ₂	— $5 \times 10^{-4} M$

Drop time = 3.1 sec. Sensitivity = $0.3 \times 3, \mu\text{A}/\text{mm}$
 $\mu = 1.0$, Temperature = 27° and pH = 6.68 ± 0.2 .

TABLE I

1. $[\text{Pt}(\text{NH}_3)(\text{NO}_2)\text{Cl}_2]^-$ <i>cis</i>	$E^{0.5} = -0.105 \text{ V Vs SCE}$
2. $[\text{Pt}(\text{NH}_3)(\text{NO}_2)\text{Cl}_2]^-$ <i>trans</i>	$E_{0.5} = -0.140 \text{ V Vs SCE}$

The plot of $\log \frac{I}{I_d - I}$ Vs E for each of the two forms is a straight line whose slope is $54 \pm 1.5 \text{ mv}$ for the *cis* form and $56 \pm 1.1 \text{ mv}$ for the *trans* form indicating a reversible one electron reduction for both the cases. It is observed that for each of the two forms of the complex the polarographic diffusion current is proportional to its concentration and the Id/C value is 4.9 ± 0.2 for the *cis* complex and 5.6 ± 0.1 for the *trans* complex.

It is quite clear from the above data that the polarographic behaviour of the two isomers is sufficiently distinct for identification purpose. The *cis* isomer is reduced at a more positive potential than the *trans* form, which is an excellent agreement with results of Crow and Westwood who have reported a similar behaviour of *cis-trans* $[\text{CO}(\text{cn})_2(\text{NO}_2)]^+$ complexes. A qualitative explanation for the observed shift in the half-wave potential for the two forms is based on a simple electrostatic argument that the preferred orientation of the *cis*-complex is due to the large internal dipole at a positive surface.

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Non-equilibrium Thermodynamic Studies of Electrokinetic Effects. Part XIII. Relaxation Time, Entropy Production Studies in Ethylene Glycol Water Mixtures

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THE entropy production in irreversible processes such as transport processes (electro-osmosis in the present case) has attracted the attention of a number of workers¹⁻³. The character of entropy production, both in steady and non-steady state is now better understood in terms of non-equilibrium thermodynamics^{4,5}. According to Prigogine⁶, the entropy production is minimum in the steady state. However, the theory of minimum entropy production is valid only when linear laws and Onsager's reciprocal relations hold good. Glansdorff⁵ and Prigogine⁴ have given a new theorem which states that for both linear and non-linear

regions the function

$$m = - \sum_i J_i \dot{X}_i \geq 0$$

the equality holding for the steady state. \dot{X}_i is the time derivatives of the force X_i , J_i being the corresponding flow. One of the purposes of the present communication is to examine the validity of the generalization in case of electro-kinetic phenomena. Another object is to determine the relaxation time Γ , for the electro-osmosis as defined by Haase⁶. It has been estimated for different water-ethyleneglycol mixtures from the formula giving the dependence of electro-osmotic pressure on time during the approach to steady state.

Experimental

Ethylene glycol was purified by vacuum distillation after drying it over calcium oxide, calcium sulphate and sodium metal and stored in sealed bottles.

Apparatus and Procedure :

The apparatus and the experimental set up adopted for the investigation were similar to those described earlier⁷. The experiments were carried out in an air thermostat having fluctuations of the order of 0.05°. The electric potential across the disc was applied through grey platinum electrodes in order to avoid the decomposition or oxidation of the system being studied.

Results and Discussion

The relaxation time, Γ , for electro-osmosis is defined as⁶

$$\Gamma = q_0 \delta / (2q\rho g\beta) \quad \dots (1)$$

where ρ is the density of the liquid, g the gravitational acceleration, q the cross-section area of the diaphragm, δ the thickness of the diaphragm, β the permeability and q_0 is the cross-section of the capillary tube in which the liquid rises during the electro-osmotic flow. Using the expression it has been deduced that the change in the height of the liquid column with time in the vertical tube is given by

$$\frac{dh}{dt} = (h_\infty - h) / \Gamma \quad \dots (2)$$

Where h_∞ is the height level corresponding to the steady state of the electro-osmotic pressure and h is the height at time t .

Integrating the equation (2) and taking into account the initial condition that $h=h_0$ for $t=0$, we obtain

$$\ln(h_\infty - h_0) - \ln(h_\infty - h) = t/\Gamma \quad \dots (3)$$

Thus Γ can be estimated from the slope of the linear plot of $\ln(h_\infty - h)$ versus t . We found linear plots in all the mixtures and a sample plot is shown in Fig 1. The values obtained are given in Table 1.

Fig. 1. Plot for the evaluation of the relaxation time.

TABLE 1—RELAXATION TIME FOR ELECTRO-OSMOTIC FLOW AT 100 VOLTS WITH ETHYLENEGLYCOL-WATER MIXTURES AT 25°C

Percentage (w/w) of ethyleneglycol	30	50	60	70
Relaxation time (Γ)	0.06	0.08	0.07	0.03

Entropy production in electro-osmosis :

Recently Haase⁸ dealt with the time dependence of the dissipation function/entropy production in electro-osmotic experiments for systems approaching a stationary (steady) state. In a steady state, the pressure difference, ΔP , and the electric potential difference, $\Delta\phi$, do not depend on time. It has also been observed that J and $d(\Delta P)/dt$ have opposite sign^{8,9} except in the stationary state, where both the quantities vanish. Thus, we have

$$J\Delta P \leq 0 \quad \text{or} \quad -J\Delta P \geq 0 \quad \dots (4)$$

The equality sign applies to the steady state. Further according to the generalisation of Glansdorff and Prigogine for electrokinetic effects it can be written as

$$m = -(I\Delta\phi + J\Delta P) \quad \dots (5)$$

In the above equation the quantity $J\Delta P$ is that part of the rate of increase of the dissipation function (product of thermodynamic temperature and entropy production) which is due to the change of the force for fixed values of the fluxes. The evolution criterion states that this quantity is negative or zero (for a steady state) for any distance from equilibrium provided the temperature is kept constant (a condition fulfilled here), the electric potential difference is fixed ($\Delta\phi=0$, see above) and the total system is closed (a condition fulfilled approximately). In the case of electro-osmotic pressure difference the relation (5) reduces to (4) because

$\Delta\phi$ is kept constant in these experiments. J and $\Delta\hat{p}$ were calculated from the slope of the curve obtained by plotting the rise of liquid against time. The values of $J\Delta\hat{p}$ for 30% ethylene glycol are plotted versus time in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Plot of $J\Delta\hat{p}$ versus t for EG-Water mixture.

The curve approaches the time axis asymptotically proving the theorem in the case of electro-osmotic flow and also it gives the evolution of entropy production. Similar plots have been obtained for other mixtures.

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